

A Systematic Review of Methodological Approaches and Gaps in the Application of Water Quality Indices (WQIS) in Nigerian Water Bodies

Kungwa, E. M, Adegbola, A. A & Olaniyan, O. S.

Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho, Nigeria

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*Corresponding Author: Kungwa, E. M.

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Abstract

Review Article

Water quality indices (WQIs) have become an essential tool for communicating the quality of water resources for drinking and different purposes globally. This method has been reported to be used in America, China, India, Iran, Brazil, Italy, Malaysia, Turkey and Spain. This review aims to identify the methodological approaches and gaps in the application of water quality indices in Nigeria water bodies. The review will encourage researchers to upscale studies using water quality indices methodologies to close knowledge gaps in this area. A total of 41 peer-reviewed articles published between 2014 and 2024 were examined, analyzing trends in water quality assessments, selection of indicators and weighting, statistical and chemometric tools, integration with machine learning and GIS, bioindicators and alternative indices. The results reveal that microbial and emerging contaminants are often excluded from WQI calculations, leading to under estimation of health risks. Furthermore, many WQI models are adapted from international frameworks without sufficient local calibration such as integrating multivariate statistics, macroinvertebrate indices, fuzzy logic, multilayer perceptron artificial neural networks and multiple linear regression models to validate water quality results. In addition, weight assignment and parameter selection remain subjective, and uncertainty quantification reduces the integrity of results. ‘Base on the output of this review, it is recommended that Researchers in water quality should always include physical and bacteriological parameters to reduce health risks associated with bacteriological contaminants. Develop a unified water quality model for Surface water, groundwater, and rainwater to enable standard measurement across the country. This will give the basis for comparing water quality results across geographical locations. Lastly, more work is required to standardize parameter selection and weight assignment in computing water quality indices.

Keywords: Water Quality Index, water quality theory, Water quality application.

I. INTRODUCTION

“Water is life” is an age-old fact that has not and cannot be disputed. It supports ecosystems, and socio-economic development of the World population. In Nigeria, where diverse populations rely heavily on surface and groundwater for drinking, other domestic uses, agriculture, and sanitation, its quality must be taken into account to guarantee public health. Globally, anthropogenic activities are

increasing in parallel with the global population (Afiatul *et al.*, 2024). The residuals from these activities, such as industrial discharge, landfill seepage, leakage from septic tanks, and agricultural runoff have introduced various contaminants into the surface and groundwater (Abu *et al.*, 2023).

This has led to a growing recognition of the need for systematic methods to evaluate and communicate water quality effectively. One such method that has

gained wide acceptance is the Water Quality Indices (WQI), a composite tool that condenses complex water quality data into a single numeric score, making it easier for policymakers, researchers, and the general public to understand water quality issues (Kachroud *et al.*, 2019). These indices facilitate comparisons between different water bodies, track changes in water quality over time, and inform management decisions. Initially, WQI was developed by Horton (1965) in the United States by selecting the ten (10) most commonly used water quality variables such as Dissolved Oxygen (DO), pH, coliforms, specific conductance, alkalinity, and chloride, among others. This has been widely applied and accepted in European, African, and Asian countries (Chidiac *et al.*, 2023). Consequently, the evolution of this invention began on a yearly basis, and many water quality indices such as the National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index (NSFWQI), the Canadian Council of Ministers of Environment Water Quality Index (CCMEWQI), the Oregon Water Quality Index (OWQI), and Weighted Arithmetic Water Quality Index (WAWQI), were developed (Paun *et al.*, 2016). These water quality indices are applied in particular areas, based on many parameters compared to specific regional standards. Moreover, they are used to illustrate annual cycles, spatio-temporal variations, and trends in water quality (Zhang *et al.*, 2019). That is to say that these indices reflect the rank of water quality in lakes, streams, rivers, and reservoirs (Kizar, 2018) Chidiac *et al.*, (2023) reported growing interest in the use of WQI methods in China, India and the United States, with 2356, 1678, and 1241 studies, respectively. Iran, Brazil, and Italy occupy the fourth, fifth, and sixth spots, respectively (409, 375, and 336 study). Malaysia and Spain have approximately the same number of studies, 321, and 320 respectively. The studies in the remaining countries decrease gradually from 303 documents in Spain to 210 documents in Turkey.

This review aims to identify the methodological approaches and gaps in the application of water quality indices in Nigerian water bodies. The review

will encourage researchers to upscale studies using water quality indices methodologies to close the knowledge gap in this area. It will help organizations and policymakers in developing standardized water quality indices methodologies for communicating water quality results that will inform efficient water treatment facility designs and improve public health.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology in this review involves a structured, transparent, and replicable process governed by Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews protocol to identify relevant peer-reviewed articles on the application of Water Quality Indices (WQIs) in Nigerian water bodies. The thematic area of interest in this review is the water quality indices methodology and water quality parameter selected for analysis.

A. Search Strategy

Four data bases that publish engineering, technology, environmental, and scientific articles were consulted: Google Scholar, Scopus, ScienceDirect (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>), and SpringerLink. The search strategy targeted foundational concepts, methodological frameworks, critiques, and interdisciplinary approaches related to WQIs in Nigerian water bodies. Search string utilized words like “water quality”, “water quality index”, “water quality theory”, “Water quality application”, and adjacent indices in search of articles published in English within ten years (2014 to 2024) ensuring a thorough and multi-faceted literature capture.

B. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Peer-reviewed articles that focused on using water quality indices models in Nigeria, published from 2014 to 2024, were selected for review. These articles covered a range of themes, starting from parameter selection to explicit WQI model, and were written in English. Journal articles having unclear empirical validity, grey literature and duplicate were excluded from the review.

Table 2.1 Articles selection process for the Review

Identified Articles	Screened Articles	Eligible	Included Articles
60	50	43	41

C. Data Extraction

Water quality index (WQI) model, parameters included, sampling methods, Author(s), year of publication, geographical location and key findings on methodology, were extracted for analysis and discussion. Mendeley desktop interface tool was used to extract and organize relevant data for this review

D. Quality Assessment

The selected articles for review were

evaluated using a checklist to assess methodological rigor. This process resulted in selecting articles with appropriate design methods, relevance and alignment with the topic thereby enhancing integrity of the review.

E. Profile of the Included Studies

Table 2.2 presents a summary of the studies, including the year of publication, geographical distribution, Author(s), and water sources.

Table 2.2 Published articles used for the review

S/N	Author(s)	Year of Publication	Location	Title
1	I. A., Okunola., A. N., Amadi., A., Idris-Nda., K., Agbasi, & L. L., Kolawole	2014	North Central	Assessment of Water Quality of Gurara Water Transfer from Gurara Dam to Lower Usuma Dam for Abuja Water Supply, FCT, Nigeria. <i>American Journal of Water Resources</i> , 2(4), 74–80. https://doi.org/10.12691/ajwr-2-4
2	Oko, O. J., Aremu, M. O., Odoh, R., Yebpella, G., & Shenge, G. A.	2014	North East	Assessment of Water Quality Index of Borehole and Well Water in Wukari Town, Taraba State, Nigeria. 4(5). www.iiste.org
3	Udousoro, I., & Umoren, I.	2014	South South	Assessment of Surface and Ground Water Quality of Uruan in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. In <i>Journal of Natural Sciences Research</i> www.iiste.org ISSN (Vol. 4, Issue 6). Online. www.iiste.org
4	Chukwuma, C., Chukwuma, C., Uba, I., Orakwe, C., & Ogbu, N.	2016	South East	Irrigation Water Quality Index Assessment of Ele River in Parts of Anambra State of Nigeria. <i>Archives of Current Research International</i> , 4(3). https://doi.org/10.9734/acri/2016/25885
5	Ojekunle, O. Z., Ojekunle, O. v., Adeyemi, A. A., Taiwo, A. G., Sangowusi, O. R., Taiwo, A. M., & Adekitan, A. A.	2016	South West	Evaluation of surface water quality indices and ecological risk assessment for heavy metals in scrap yard neighbourhood. <i>SpringerPlus</i> , 5(1). https://doi.org/10.1186/s40064-016-2158-9
6	Olowe, B., Oluyeye, J., & Famurewa, O	2016	South West	An Assessment of Drinking Water Quality Using Water Quality Index in Ado-Ekiti and Environs, Nigeria. <i>American Chemical Science Journal</i> , 12(2), 1–7. https://doi.org/10.9734/acsj/2016/22445

7	Ogbozige, F., Adie, D., Igboro, S., & Giwa, A.	2017	North West	Evaluation of the Water Quality of River Kaduna, Nigeria Using Water Quality Index. <i>Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management</i> , 21(6), 1119. https://doi.org/10.4314/jasem.v21i6.21
8	Okanlawon, M. O., Olasehinde, P. I., Abdullahi, I. N., Amadi, A. N., Waziri, N. M., & Unuevho, C. I.	2017	North Central	Water Quality Determination Around Gold and Manganese Mining Area Using Metal Pollution Index and Water Quality Index in South-western Part of Tegna North Central Nigeria. <i>International Journal of Innovative Research and Development</i> , 6(11). https://doi.org/10.24940/ijird/2017/v6/i11/nov17029
9	Yonnana, E., Yamta, S., Kaigama, I., & Bedeson, A.	2017	North East	Assessment of Water Quality for Goro Dong (Lake) and Its Suitability for Consumption and Domestic Use by the Immediate Lake Communities in Numan, Adamawa State Nigeria. <i>Journal of Geography, Environment and Earth Science International</i> , 12(4), 1–8. https://doi.org/10.9734/jgeesi/2017/37517
10	Apagu Ankidawa, B., Linus Sunday, U., & Vanke, I.	2018	North Central	Water quality index and hydrogeochemistry of Otukpo area, Benue State, North Central Nigeria. In <i>J. Trop. Resour. Sustain. Sci</i> (Vol. 6).
11	Ejoh, A. S., Unuakpa, B. A., Ibadin, F. H., & Edeki, S. O.	2018	South South	Dataset on the assessment of water quality and water quality index of Ubogo and Egini rivers, Udu LGA, Delta State Nigeria. <i>Data in Brief</i> , 19. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2018.06.053
12	Sulaiman, M. B., Maigari, A. U., & Ringim, S. A.	2018	North East	Quality Index of Drinking Water from Different Sources in Gombe Town, Northern Nigeria. In <i>J. Chem Soc. Nigeria</i> (Vol. 43, Issue 4).
13	Igbemi, I. A., Nwaogazie, I. L., Akaranta, O., & Abu, G. O.	2019	South South	Water Quality Assessment by Pollution Indices in Eastern Obolo Coastline Communities of Nigeria. <i>American Journal of Water Resources</i> , 7(3), 111–120. https://doi.org/10.12691/ajwr-7-3-4
14	Nnorom, I., Ewuzie, U., & Eze, S.	2019	South East	Multivariate statistical approach and water quality assessment of natural springs and other drinking water sources in Southeastern Nigeria. <i>Heliyon</i> , 5. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01123
15	Esme Atojunere, E., & Ogedengbe, K.	2019	South West	Evaluating Water Quality Indicators of Some Water Sources in the Bitumen-Rich Areas of Ondo State, Nigeria. <i>International Journal of Environmental Pollution and Remediation</i> , 9–22. https://doi.org/10.11159/ijep.2019.002
16	Mgbenu, C. N., & Egbueri, J. C	2019	South East	The hydrogeochemical signatures, quality indices and health risk assessment of water resources in Umunya district, southeast Nigeria. <i>Applied Water Science</i> , 9(1). https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-019-0900-5
17	Olasoji, S. O., Oyewole, N. O., Abiola, B., & Edokpayi, J. N.	2019	South West	Water quality assessment of surface and groundwater sources using a water quality index method: A case study of a peri-urban town in southwest, Nigeria. <i>Environments - MDPI</i> , 6(2). https://doi.org/10.3390/environments6020023

18	Tarawou, T., & Aigberua, A	2019	South South	Water Quality Index (WQI) Assessment along Inland Fresh Waters of Taylor Creek in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. In <i>Journal of Environmental Treatment Techniques</i> (Vol. 7, Issue 3). http://www.jett.dormaj.com
19	Aigberua, A., Tarawou, T., & Erepamowei, Y.	2020	South South	Environmental Assessment of Imiringi River in South-South Nigeria: The Water Quality Index Approach. <i>Current World Environment</i> , 15(1), 59–67. https://doi.org/10.12944/CWE.15.1.09
20	Egbueri, J., & Mgbenu, C.	2020	South East	Chemometric analysis for pollution source identification and human health risk assessment of water resources in Ojoto Province, southeast Nigeria. <i>Applied Water Science</i> , 10, 1-18. https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-020-01180-9
21	Wali, S. U., Alias, N., & Harun, S. bin.	2020	North West	Quality reassessment using water quality indices and hydrochemistry of groundwater from the Basement Complex section of Kaduna Basin, NW Nigeria. In <i>SN Applied Sciences</i> (Vol. 2, Issue 10). Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-03536-x
22	Olumuyiwa, F. O., & Olayemi, O. O.	2020	South West	Assessment of Water Quality Index and Irrigation Indices in Ese Odo Area of Ondo State, Southwestern Nigerian. <i>International Annals of Science</i> , 9(1), 174–187. https://doi.org/10.21467/ias.9.1.174-187
23	Umar, N. D., Omonona, O. v., & Okogbue, C. O.	2021	North Central	Groundwater Quality Assessment Using Multivariate Analysis and Water Quality Index in some Saline Fields of Central Nigeria. <i>Journal of the Nigerian Society of Physical Sciences</i> , 3(4), 267–277. https://doi.org/10.46481/jnsps.2021.183
24	Iwar, R., Utsev, J., & Hassan, M	2021	North Central	Assessment of heavy metal and physico-chemical pollution loadings of River Benue water at Makurdi using water quality index (WQI) and multivariate statistics. <i>Applied Water Science</i> , 11. https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-021-01456-8
25	Ubah, J., Orakwe, L., Ogbu, K., Awu, J., Ahaneku, I., & Chukwuma, E	2021	South East	Forecasting water quality parameters using artificial neural network for irrigation purposes. <i>Scientific Reports</i> , 11. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-04062-5
26	Iloba, K. I., Akawo, N. O., & Godwin, P. I.	2021	South South	Assessment of Anwai river water quality using the weighted arithmetic water quality index (WQI) in delta state, Nigeria. <i>Journal of Applied and Natural Science</i> , 13(3), 913–922. https://doi.org/10.31018/jans.v13i3.2758
27	Peremobowei Beldin Kpikpi, & Onome Augustina Bubu-Davies.	2021	South South	Evaluation of water quality index in some artificial aquatic environments in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. <i>Magna Scientia Advanced Research and Reviews</i> , 1(3), 013–021. https://doi.org/10.30574/msarr.2021.1.3.0015
28	Unamba, U., Nwajagu, E., Munta, S., Unamba, K. U., Medjor, E. A., & Nwajagu, E. S	2021	North East	Assessment of Water Quality Index for Taraba State Water Supply Agency's Sources: A Case Study of Jalingo Metropolis. In <i>International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology</i> (Vol. 8). www.ijiset.com

29	Amuntse, E., Alhassan, E., Ogbaji, G., Paul, S., & Ibrahim, A	2022	North East	Evaluation of Quality Index of Borehole Water in Marmara and New Site Communities of Wukari, Nigeria. <i>UMYU Scientifica</i> , 1(1), 114–121. https://doi.org/10.47430/usci.1122.015
30	Agbasi, J. C., & Egbueri, J. C.	2022	South East	Assessment of PTEs in water resources by integrating HHRISK code, water quality indices, multivariate statistics, and ANNs. <i>Geocarto International</i> , 37(25). https://doi.org/10.1080/10106049.2022.2034990
31	Sadiq, Q., Ezeamaka, C. K., Daful, M. G., & Mustafa, I. A.	2022	North West	Evaluation of the Water Quality of River Kaduna, Nigeria Using Water Quality Index. <i>Environmental Technology and Science Journal</i> , 13(1), 28–40. https://doi.org/10.4314/etsj.v13i1.3
32	Babika, Z. M., & Tukur, A. I	2022	North West	Spatial correlation of groundwater pollutants with the vulnerability index in Kano Metropolis, North-western Nigeria. <i>Water Practice and Technology</i> , 17(12). https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2022.141
33	Butu, A. W., Emeribe, C. N., Muoka, I. O., Emeribe, O. F., & Ogbomida, E. T.	2022	North West	Downstream Effects of Industrial Effluents Discharge on Some Physicochemical Parameters and Water Quality Index of River Rido, Kaduna State, Nigeria. <i>Tropical Aquatic and Soil Pollution</i> , 2(2), 90–108. https://doi.org/10.53623/tasp.v2i2.100
34	Ejeomo, C., Oghoje, S. U., & Obayagbona, N. O	2022	South South	Water Quality Index classification of ground water samples collected from Opete, community, Delta State, Southern Nigeria. <i>Dutse Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences</i> , 8(3b), 25–33. https://doi.org/10.4314/dujopas.v8i3b.3
35	Ezea, V. C., Ihedioha, J. N., Abugu, H. O., & Ekere, N. R	2022		A multi-criteria approach to drinking and irrigation water assessment of spring water in Igbo-Etiti, Nigeria. <i>Applied Water Science</i> , 12(9). https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-022-01747-8
36	Akakuru, O., Njoku, U., Obinna- Akakuru, A., Akudinobi, B., Obasi, P., Aigbadon, G., & Onyeawwuna, U.	2023	South East	Non-carcinogenic health risk assessment and predicting of pollution indexing of groundwater around Osisoma, Nigeria, using artificial neural networks and multi-linear modeling principles. <i>Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment</i> , 1-31. https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-023-02398-0
37	Ebuete, A. W., Puanoni, N. I., Ebuete, Y. I., & Ebuete, E.	2023	South South	Water Quality Index (NSFWQI) of the River Nun, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. <i>American Journal of Environment and Climate</i> , 2(2), 15–22. https://doi.org/10.54536/ajec.v2i2.598
38	Kabari, S., Amarachi, P. O., Ochuko, J. E., & Felix, E.	2023	South South	Water quality evaluation using water quality index and pollution model in selected communities in Gbaramatu Kingdom, Niger Delta, Nigeria. <i>African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology</i> , 17(6), 118–134. https://doi.org/10.5897/ajest2023.3193
39	Omeka, M	2023	South East	Evaluation and prediction of irrigation water quality of an agricultural district, SE Nigeria: an integrated heuristic GIS-based and machine learning approach. <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i> , 1-26. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-25119-6

40	Kayode, M. O., Tomori, W. B., Okoronkwo, E. A., & Adiat, K. A. N.	2024	South West	Seasonal variation of groundwater quality in a basement complex geology of Ado Ekiti Nigeria using water quality index model. <i>Journal of Umm Al-Qura University for Applied Sciences</i> . https://doi.org/10.1007/s43994-024-00195-1
41	Mshelia, S. S., & Mbaya, A. Y.	2024	North West	suitability of groundwater quality for drinking using water quality index in kano metropolis, nigeria. <i>fudma journal of sciences</i> , 8(1), 69–77. https://doi.org/10.33003/fjs-2024-0801-2217

III. RESULTS

Water quality in Nigeria has evolved from traditional models developed by Horton in 1965, with the focus on physicochemical parameters. Recently, WQIs studies can integrate more sophisticated frameworks such as multivariate statistics, Chemometric analysis, entropy weighted, multiple pollution indices, and machine learning (Mgbenu & Egbueri, 2019; Egbueri *et al.*, 2020; Agbasi & Egbueri, 2023; Omeka, 2023). In some studies, pollution indices, spatial analysis, and the degree of health risk are assessed to elicit the quality of water (Nnorom *et al.*, 2019).

A. WQI model approaches and tools.

- (i) *Parameter Selection and Weighting*: Most studies use standard physicochemical parameters (pH, TDS, heavy metals, etc.) in determining water quality. However, there is no uniformity or guidelines for the selection of parameters. For instance, Ebuete *et al.*, 2023 characterized the water quality of the River Nun at various reaches for six months (dry and wet season) using nine (9) physiochemical and biological parameters. Ejeomo, *et al.*, (2022) classified ground water from Opete, community, Delta State, Southern Nigeria, using eight (8) physicochemical parameters. Furthermore, the weight assigned to the parameter depends on the model of WQI used. For instance, WAWQI, weights are assigned based on perceived importance or statistical methods such as principal component analysis (Thomas, 2023).
- (ii) *Statistical and Chemometric Tools*: Multivariate statistics (PCA, cluster analysis) are widely used

to identify pollution sources and reduce dimensionality, improving the interpretability of WQI results. Iwar, R., Utsev, T., and Martina, H. used multivariate statistics to assess heavy metal and physico-chemical pollution loadings of river Benue water at Makurdi and concluded that increased anthropogenic activities were responsible for the deteriorating quality of the water (Akakuru *et al.*, 2023; Iwar *et al.*, 2021).

- (iii) *Integration with Machine Learning and GIS*: In forecasting water quality parameters using artificial neural networks for irrigation purposes, multilayer perceptron artificial neural networks (MLP-ANNs) and multiple linear regression models (MLR) were integrated and validated to predict the IWQ. Physicochemical parameters were used as input variables, and MAR, SAR, PI, KR, SSP, and PS as output variables to predict and visualize water quality trends (Ubah *et al.*, 2021; Akakuru *et al.*, 2023; Omeka, 2023 ;).

Bioindicators and Alternative Indices: Some studies employ macroinvertebrate-based indices and fuzzy logic models to complement or critique traditional WQI approaches. For instance, Oladipo *et al.*, (2021) made comparison between fuzzy logic and water quality index methods in assessing water quality of Ikare community, Southwestern Nigeria, and results revealed the superiority of Fuzzy Logic over WQI methods because FL enables equal consideration to the measured values and surface water quality (SWQ) standards, whereas WQI considers only the water quality standards for evaluation (Oladipo *et al.*, 2021; Edegbene *et al.*, 2019).

Table 3.1 Research Coverage Matrix table

Parameter	Surface Water	Groundwater	Combined Surface & Groundwater
Physicochemical Only	5	6	1
Microbial Included	4	5	1
Machine Learning Used	3	2	0
GIS/Spatial Analysis	4	2	0
Health Risk Assessment	3	4	1

Fig3.1 Graph showing Research coverage Matrix and WQI methodology

B. Application Outcomes and Water Quality Status.

(i) *Surface Water:* WQI application to rivers and creeks often reveals significant spatial and seasonal variability, with many sites classified as "poor" or "unfit" for drinking, especially in industrial and urbanized regions (Iwegbue *et al.*, 2022). The study on Hydro-geochemical analysis and quality evaluation of surface water in the Mamu River basin, southeastern Nigeria, suggested that the surface water is unfit for ingestion when compared with the WHO and Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) standards (Ayogu *et al.*, 2020). Assessment of anthropogenic activities impacts on the water quality of Asa River around Amilengbe area,

Ilorin, Kwara state, Nigeria shows the water is fit for agricultural purposes (irrigation farming) but unfit for drinking (Zacchaeus *et al.*, 2020).

(ii) *Groundwater:* Groundwater sources generally fare better, with many studies reporting "good" or "excellent" quality. Kwami, *et al.*, 2018 assessed the Water quality index for the groundwater in Gombe and environs, North-east Nigeria revealed that majority of groundwater samples fall in good category (66%) others fall in excellent category (44%) indicating groundwater is fit for drinking purposes (Kwami, 2018). Although localized contamination from heavy metals and microbial agents is common, for instance, Wali *et al.*, 2020 reassessed water quality using WQIs

and hydrochemistry of groundwater from the Basement Complex section of Kaduna Basin, Northwest Nigeria, and result shows groundwater is unsuitable for industrial use since it is undersaturated with calcium carbonate. (Wali, *et al.*, 2020; Ayejoto *et al.*, 2022; Shuaibu *et al.*, 2024).

- (i) *Health Risk Assessments*: Integration of WQI with health risk models highlights the vulnerability of children and the need to address both carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risks (Ayejoto *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, a study on multi-criteria approach to drinking and irrigation water assessed spring water in Igbo-Etiti, Nigeria and result showed a probable risk associated with the consumption of the spring water (Ezea, *et al.*, 2022).

C. Critiques, Limitations, and Gaps

- (i) *Parameter Omission*: Microbial and emerging contaminants are often excluded from WQI calculations, leading to underestimation of health risks (Olasoji *et al.*, 2019; Adesakin *et al.*, 2020; Ugbaja & Ephraim, 2019).
- (ii) *Site Specificity and Adaptation*: Many WQI models are adapted from international frameworks without sufficient local calibration, reducing their relevance (Nnorom *et al.*, 2019; Egbueri *et al.*, 2020).
- (iii) *Uncertainty and Subjectivity*: Weight assignment and parameter selection remain subjective, and uncertainty quantification is rarely addressed (Egbueri *et al.*, 2020; Oladipo *et al.*, 2021).

IV. DISCUSSION

The application of WQIs in Nigeria has advanced significantly, with methodological innovations enhancing the accuracy and relevance of water quality assessments. The integration of multivariate statistics, machine learning, and GIS has improved source identification and spatial mapping, while health risk assessments provide a more holistic view of water safety (Mgbenu & Egbueri, 2019; Nnorom *et al.*, 2019; Ubah *et al.*, 2021; Akakuru *et al.*, 2023; Omeka, 2023; Agbasi & Egbueri, 2023).

However, persistent gaps remain, particularly in the inclusion of microbial and emerging contaminants, local adaptation of indices, and uncertainty quantification (Olasoji *et al.*, 2019). The reliance on physicochemical parameters alone can mask significant health risks, especially in regions with high microbial contamination (Adesakin *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, the subjectivity in parameter selection and weighting underscores the need for standardized, context-specific frameworks.

V. CONCLUSION

WQIs are indispensable for water quality assessment in Nigeria, but methodological gaps—especially regarding parameter selection, microbial inclusion, and local adaptation—limit their full potential. Advances in statistical, computational, and interdisciplinary approaches offer promising avenues for more robust and context-specific WQI frameworks.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following is recommended as measures to bridge the methodological gap in the use of water quality models:

- (i) Researchers in water quality should always include physical and bacteriological parameters to reduce the health risk associated with bacteriological contaminants.
- (ii) A unified water quality model for Surface, ground, and rainwater should be developed to enable standard measurement across the country. This will give the basis for comparison of water quality across geographical locations.
- (iii) More work is required to standardize parameter selection and weight assignment in computing water quality indices.

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